

Design and Validation of a Lightweight 1D CNN for Affective Touch Classification in Soft Plush Companions

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Abstract

Soft, sensorized companions offer a physically safe and emotionally intuitive interface for socially assistive technologies, yet their deformability and multichannel tactile sensing complicate the robust interpretation of human affect. This study presents a complete open-source MATLAB-based framework for the development and validation of compact deep learning models for affective touch recognition in soft interactive companions, with the trained model designed for eventual deployment on an ESP32-class microcontroller. As a primary contribution, a diverse FAIR-compliant dataset of 1326 labelled gesture sequences collected from 25 participants spanning children, teenagers, and adults is made publicly available, providing a reusable resource for future research in affective touch recognition. Through systematic architecture and hyperparameter exploration across 468 CNN models, the study identifies compact dilated one-dimensional convolutional neural networks (1D CNNs) as the most effective solution, with a 13.2k-parameter model achieving 75% test accuracy and 85% mean leave-one-subject-out cross-validation accuracy. Theoretical inference-time analysis shows that quantized deployment requires 3.2 MMAC per window, compatible with 20 Hz real-time operation on the target microcontroller. PC-based real-time simulation with the physical toy streaming sensor data demonstrates that the CNN resolves subtle social touches that the previous heuristic system failed to detect, whereas high-force negative interactions are captured more reliably by trivial threshold-based logic. The resulting hybrid inference pipeline – instantaneous heuristic filtering followed by CNN-based nuanced gesture classification – is proposed as the embedded deployment strategy. The study demonstrates that emotionally meaningful, privacy-preserving touch interpretation is computationally feasible for direct embedding within soft therapeutic companions, with hardware integration and field validation addressed in a forthcoming study.

Keywords: affective computing; machine learning; tactile emotion recognition; socially assistive robots; autism-focused assistive technology

1. Introduction

Emotionally responsive interactive systems have become increasingly relevant in socially assistive robotics (SAR), education, and rehabilitation. These systems aim to detect human affect and respond in ways that promote engagement, calmness, or social learning [1]. Among various sensory modalities, touch is one of the most direct and emotionally significant communication channels, particularly for children and individuals with autism spectrum disorder (ASD), who often find visual or verbal cues overwhelming [2,3] or vice versa - characteristic altered engagement of visual attention [4,5] and listening difficulties in the perception of verbal and auditory information [6].

Traditional SARs such as NAO, Pepper, KASPAR, PARO and “Joy for All” products have shown benefits in therapy and eldercare [7,8,9,10,11] but their mechanical parts make them fragile in case of rough handling, and in some cases reliance on external computation restricts physical interaction and emotional authenticity [12,13,14,15]. Soft, sensorized devices – such as plush interactive companions – address these issues by allowing natural tactile engagement while remaining physically safe and ensuring robustness. Their flexibility, however, increases the number of degrees of freedom, since their spatial state is not well defined and may introduce new challenges during signal processing, complicating gesture interpretation. Emotion recognition is a challenging task [16], which may need a model fine-tuned to a

particular individual for sufficient accuracy [17], however such retraining usually is not feasible, because use-cases mostly involve subjects who did not participate in training data collection sessions.

The system described in this work builds on previous developments in soft, sensorized interactive plush toys designed for use in therapy and education [18]. Earlier prototypes use heuristic threshold-based algorithms to classify affective touches as “positive” or “negative.” While intuitive, these algorithms often misclassified complex gestures – such as hugs or other gestures, which involved multi-sensor contacts – and produced inconsistent feedback. Furthermore, clinical assistants, who used these plush toys during therapeutic sessions, reported difficulty eliciting positive reactions, moreover negative feedback occasionally reinforced undesirable behavior [19,20,21,22,23].

To overcome these drawbacks, this study introduces a deep learning–based affective touch classifier [24] ready to be integrated into a soft interactive toy. The classifier uses real-time sensor data to distinguish gestures such as stroking, scratching, holding, or hitting, and map them to affective categories. The focus is on achieving high accuracy, short latency, and low computational complexity theoretically compatible with an embedded design running on a microcontroller, with actual physical hardware integration and validation addressed as the next step in our future work. The system must operate autonomously without external computing resources or network connectivity – these requirements are critical for reliability and privacy in therapeutic settings.

This research contributes an end-to-end framework for affective touch recognition, encompassing (1) data collection from human–toy interaction; (2) structured data preprocessing and augmentation; (3) systematic CNN architecture testing and optimization; and (4) validation on real-time in-the-field data. The methods and results demonstrate that efficient, low-power embedded machine learning (ML) model can provide real-time emotional responsiveness comparable to more resource-intensive systems.

The goal of this study is to design and validate a deep learning system that enables a soft interactive toy to interpret tactile input in real time on embedded hardware. The main objectives are:

1. To collect and preprocess a large, diverse dataset of tactile gestures from children and adults to ensure generalization, which is a weak point in some of the available solutions [31], and to publish it as a FAIR-compliant open resource for the research community;
2. To develop and optimize lightweight one-dimensional convolutional neural networks (1D CNNs) for multi-sensor gesture classification;
3. To analyze the computational requirements of the developed model and verify its theoretical compatibility with the ESP32-WROVER-E microcontroller, ensuring that real-time embedded performance is feasible;
4. To qualitatively compare the new model’s performance with the previous heuristic algorithm in terms of classification accuracy, latency, and user response consistency.

By meeting these objectives, the system establishes a scalable foundation for emotionally intelligent, soft-bodied therapeutic smart companions that can interpret human affect through touch – safely, efficiently, and in a robust design.

2. Related Works

Research in affective robotics, emotion recognition, and tactile interaction has evolved rapidly over the last two decades. Early socially assistive robots (SARs) focused on visual and auditory cues for affect interpretation [32,33,34,35], but recent work highlights tactile interaction as an equally significant channel of emotional communication [36,37,38,39]. This section outlines key developments in three intersecting domains: socially assistive robots and human–robot interaction, affective touch and emotion classification, and therapeutic use for individuals with communication or developmental disorders.

2.1. Socially Assistive Robots and Human–Robot Interaction

SARs aim to provide cognitive or emotional support through social interaction rather than mechanical assistance [35,40]. Systems such as KASPAR, NAO, and PARO have demonstrated measurable benefits in therapy, education, and eldercare [13,41,42]. These robots can foster emotional expression, imitation, and social engagement, particularly in individuals with ASD, dementia, or depression [1,15].

However, the majority of existing SARs rely on rigid mechanical components and surface-mounted sensors, limiting their physical interactivity. Rigid structures are prone to damage under strong contact, thus system’s robustness is of particular importance, since children with ASD may be rough during an interaction [43,44]. In contrast, soft-bodied systems – based on deformable materials and compliant sensor arrays – enable safe, expressive physical interaction while retaining emotional resonance [45]. These devices align more closely with human tactile expectations and can capture affective nuances through distributed sensing.

The present research builds on this transition toward soft, sensorized companions that emphasize haptic over visual or auidial communication. Unlike humanoid robots, which simulate empathy through programmed gestures, soft interactive devices can interpret and provide appropriate responses, fostering bidirectional emotional interaction.

2.2. Affective Touch and Emotion Classification

Touch is a primary channel of emotional communication [25]. Gentle, continuous contact typically conveys comfort or affection, while abrupt or forceful contact signals discomfort or anger [26, 27]. The C-tactile afferent system in human skin is tuned to slow, soft stroking, which is physiologically linked to feelings of safety and attachment [3]. Translating such affective nuances into robotic perception requires distributed tactile sensing and algorithms capable of interpreting complex temporal patterns.

Recent studies have explored affective touch classification using ML and artificial neural networks (ANN). Approaches based on convolutional and recurrent architectures have shown strong performance in recognizing gestures from capacitive, piezoresistive, or vibration sensors [24,28,29,30,31]. However, most of these approaches rely on external computation, limiting their use in portable or embedded devices. The present work addresses this gap by developing a compact, real-time CNN model for affective touch recognition embedded directly in a soft smart toy platform. The rationale for selecting a CNN-based approach over recurrent architectures is discussed in Section 3.3. By optimizing architecture depth, filter size, and dilation, the system achieves robust gesture classification with low latency. This capability enables emotionally meaningful feedback, supporting behavioral learning and engagement in autistic children during therapeutic sessions.

Touch-mediated affect recognition has become a central topic in affective computing. Affective touch datasets – usually based on records from capacitive, piezoresistive, or piezoelectric sensors – have enabled supervised machine learning methods to classify gestures by emotional valence or intensity [46]. Both traditional machine learning and modern deep learning techniques have been used successfully to train affective touch classifiers [31]. The choice of the method largely depends on the data available and the complexity of the task, as in tackling other classification problems. The available computational resources should also be kept in mind, as it will directly influence the performance of the system.

Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have shown strong performance in tactile and biosignal classification due to their efficiency in modeling local temporal dependencies [47]. 1D CNNs in particular have been applied successfully to electrocardiogram (ECG) classification [48], accelerometry [49], and other sequential data domains, combining high accuracy with low computational cost. These properties make CNNs well suited for embedded gesture recognition tasks, which are the main topic of this study.

Studies integrating dilated convolutions – which expand the receptive field of a CNN without increasing the number of parameters – have further improved recognition of long-duration gestures such as stroking or holding [50]. Comparable techniques have been applied in human affect recognition systems that analyze multimodal input, including voice, facial expression, and touch [51].

Despite these advances, most tactile affective systems remain dependent on high-power processors or cloud infrastructure, constraining their portability. Edge-based inference remains underexplored, particularly for multichannel capacitive input in soft interactive companion platforms.

2.3. Therapeutic and Educational Applications

Affective robotics plays an increasingly important role in therapy and education, especially for populations with impaired social communication. In autism therapy, SARs help structure interactions through predictable, repeatable responses that promote emotional regulation and imitation learning [1,52]. For elderly individuals, tactile interaction with companion robots reduces loneliness and depressive symptoms, reinforcing the therapeutic value of affective physical contact [15].

While humanoid or zoomorphic robots such as PARO have demonstrated clinical benefits, their reliance on mechanical actuation limits scalability. Soft interactive toys provide a low-cost, robust, and emotionally safe alternative, capable of offering similar affective benefits through tactile sensing and behavioral feedback. Integrating deep learning into these systems enhances the ability to interpret human affect autonomously, supporting therapy sessions.

Recent research trends emphasize emotionally adaptive systems – devices capable not only of detecting emotion, but also of modulating their responses accordingly [17]. Such adaptability is critical for maintaining engagement over long-term use. The proposed system aligns with this direction by enabling real-time affective classification and feedback entirely on-device, laying the groundwork for personalized therapeutic companions.

The first generation of our soft plush companions, equipped with a heuristic touch–response algorithm, has already been introduced in trial therapeutic and educational sessions with children formally diagnosed with ASD. In these sessions, conducted in collaboration with rehabilitation centers and special preschools, the toys were used as supporting materials within therapist-led activities, not as stand-alone therapeutic agents: specialists structured the interaction, and the plush robots functioned as mediating tools to elicit engagement, emotional expression, and social communication, alongside standard rehabilitation methods. The design of these sessions, the interdisciplinary four-phase research methodology, and preliminary qualitative findings on usability, engagement, and perceived therapeutic potential are reported in detail in a separate publication focused on psychological and educational aspects [53]. By contrast, the present work concentrates exclusively on the technical layer of the system – gesture recognition from tactile and inertial signals, classifier design, and embedded feasibility.

2.4. The Goal of the Study

The current study positions itself at the intersection of soft interactive assistants, affective computing, and embedded AI. By merging soft tactile sensing with efficient 1D CNN inference, it demonstrates that emotion recognition using affective touch can be achieved also in embedded systems running on limited computational resources. The approach contributes to ongoing efforts to make socially assistive systems more affordable, resilient, and robust.

This work thus extends the trajectory of SAR research from rigid robots toward soft, emotionally responsive devices, capable of perceiving and responding to affective touch in real time. The combination of deep learning–based gesture classification and theoretical validation of embedded hardware feasibility represents a technical and conceptual step toward emotionally aware and safe therapeutic technologies.

The main contributions of the present work are an embeddable 1D-CNN for a soft interactive toy, a FAIR dataset [54] that contains all the collected training data, as well as a complete Processing/MATLAB pipeline [55] for the development of such a system.

3. Materials and Methods

This section summarizes the development process for the affective touch classification system, including system design, dataset collection, preprocessing, model training, and real-time validation. The focus is on reproducible, efficient methods that ensure high model accuracy while maintaining theoretical feasibility for embedded deployment; physical hardware integration is addressed in a forthcoming study.

3.1. System Design

As was mentioned before, this study focuses on improving the algorithmic part of an interactive plush toy that was developed previously [18]. A few variations of such toys have been developed, which are presented in Figure 1(a).

Figure 1. Soft plush companions with integrated capacitive sensors.

(a) – Soft plush companions; (b) – Sensors placement

However, all the variations share the same hardware part. The toys have several capacitive touch sensors that are integrated under the plush layer. These are located in the extremities, ears, head, neck, nose, tail, back, belly, see Figure 1(b), as well as a proximity sensor, which senses approaching objects (e.g. a hand) from all sides. Along with these signals, a cumulative signal is also sent, which combines all the mentioned signals. Besides the capacitive sensors, the toys also have a 3-axis accelerometer. Accelerometer signals are particularly helpful in detecting such gestures as throwing, pushing the toy violently or lifting it upside down. See Table 1 for a detailed definition of the signal data. However, for processing in a 1D CNN model, the accelerometer signals are replaced with a magnitude value, using formula $Acc_{magn} = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}$.

Sampling occurs at 100 Hz. All electronics – including sensors, Bluetooth module, and the microcontroller (MCU) – are enclosed in a compact, rechargeable battery-powered unit. The system is capable of autonomous operation using the integrated MCU. For control and fine-tuning, as well as for testing the trained models on real-time field data, the system is capable of sending sensor data via Bluetooth connection, which helps to avoid disruptions in capacitive sensor functioning. The system sends data as newline-terminated strings containing 15 integers, which are separated by one or more spaces and are defined as follows:

Table 1. Sensor data definition

No.	Description of the parameter
1	Cumulative signal, based on all the capacitive sensors
2	Cumulative signal, based on the capacitive sensors placed inside extremities
3-5	Signal from the capacitive sensor in the ears / head / neck
6	Signal from the proximity capacitive sensor
7-10	Signal from the capacitive sensor in the nose / tail / back / belly
11-13	X / Y / Z component of the accelerometer signal
14	Timestamp of the data frame, obtained from the MCU's clock
15	Delay in <i>ms</i> from the previous measurement

The original version of the interactive toys has a heuristic algorithm, which analyzes and classifies these sensor signals. It tries to determine whether the gesture has a positive or a negative emotional connotation

on the bases of signal timing and amplitude analysis. If the gesture is deemed positive, the eyes turn green, and the toy produces a sound of satisfaction (e.g. purring). If the gesture is deemed negative, the eyes turn red, and it produces an angry/dissatisfied sound (e.g. shrieking). However, the heuristic algorithm failed to provide consistent and predictable reactions. Field tests have shown that the heuristic algorithm is sensitive to environmental conditions, such as humidity, and to the subject’s physicality, such as hand size. These problems made it necessary to develop an algorithm based on more robust models.

It is important to note that the present study focuses exclusively on the development, training, and validation of the gesture classification model and the accompanying software framework. A complete, open-source MATLAB-based pipeline has been developed and made publicly available at a repository [55], covering the full workflow from raw sensor data acquisition and preprocessing, through systematic CNN architecture exploration, to PC-based real-time classification simulation. This framework provides a reusable and extensible foundation for developing and testing ML models for affective touch recognition in smart interactive companions, and constitutes a primary contribution of this work. All real-time tests described in the following sections were conducted in this PC-based simulation environment, with the physical toy connected via Bluetooth as a live sensor data source. The computational and memory requirements of the selected models are analyzed theoretically to confirm feasibility for deployment on the ESP32-WROVER-E microcontroller. The actual integration of the trained model into the embedded hardware, along with direct inference time measurements and field testing in therapeutic sessions, is designated as the subject of a forthcoming study.

3.2. Data Collection

Participants and gestures

A total of 25 participants (14 female, 11 male) contributed to the tactile data training dataset, including 8 adults, 9 teenagers, and 8 kindergarten-age children. Each participant recorded 17 gestures that were repeated three times, resulting in 51 samples per participant. Additional 51 “at rest” samples were recorded without human interaction, yielding a total of 1326 labelled gesture sequences prior to data cleaning and augmentation. Gesture definition is found in Table 2. They mostly follow such common taxonomies as found in [56], with a special focus on gestures that the original struggled with.

Table 2. Gesture definitions

Name of the gesture (Label)	Description of the gesture
At rest	Toy is laying still in different orientations
Back stroke 1 / 2	Stroking toy’s back, while the toy is placed on a table (1) or while it is being held in hands (2)
Ear scratch 1 / 2	Scratching the head between ears, while the toy is placed on a table (1) or while it is being held in hands (2)
Head stroke 1 / 2	Stroking toy’s head, while the toy is placed on a table (1) or while it is being held in hands (2)
Hold in hands	Toy is picked from the table and is held in hands
Hold strong	Toy held in hands, then it is pushed with force against person’s body and held in that position
Neck scratch 1 / 2	Scratching the neck between ears, while the toy is placed on a table (1) or while it is being held in hands (2)
Tail hit 1 / 2	One energetic strike on the toy’s back, while the toy is placed on a table (1) or while it is being held in hands (2)
Tail pull	One energetic pull of the tail, while holding the toy in hands
Tail scratch 1 / 2	Scratching the back near the tail, while the toy is placed on a table (1) or while it is being held in hands (2)
Tail tap 1 / 2	Light tapping on the back near the tail, while the toy is placed on a table (1) or while it is being held in hands (2)

The gesture set encompassed positive (e.g., stroking, scratching), neutral (e.g. holding, resting), and negative (e.g. hitting, tail pulling) interactions. Each gesture was performed under two conditions: while the toy was resting on a table (e.g., “Back stroke 1”) and while the toy was held in hands (e.g., “Back stroke 2”),

enabling the model to learn gesture variability across contexts. Ultimately this helped to avoid the model from being overwhelmed with sensor signals, which fire simultaneously while the toy is being held in hands.

While not exhaustive, the gesture set was chosen to test model's ability to distinguish between extremely similar classes, such as *Tail tapping* and *Tail scratching*. Gesture label, timestamp, and sample length are encoded into the filename. The dataset is publicly available in the repository [54] and is published according to FAIR principles [57].

Recording procedure

Data collection was automated using the *Gesture Recorder* tool, adapted from Jon Froehlich's Physical Computing repository [58]. The version adapted for the hardware of plush interactive toys can be found at repository [55] in folder "Processing". GUI of the tool is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Gesture Recorder tool used to collect training data

Before a data recording session, the soft toy is paired with a computer via a Bluetooth link. The Bluetooth driver creates a serial port used for data exchange. The program establishes a link with the toy by opening this port, then it instructs the user which gesture needs to be recorded and records all sensor data. A three-second countdown begins upon pressing the space bar, after which recording starts automatically. Recording stops upon a second press, ensuring clean segmentation. The program cycles through all gestures sequentially, generating labelled and timestamped CSV files for each sample.

Preprocessing and data management

Data preprocessing was implemented in MATLAB through a modular workflow and is available in the repository in folder "MATLAB" [55]:

1. **Anonymization and organization** – *Gesture Recorder* tool saves data obtained from each subject in a separate folder. Data from these folders containing samples of individual participants are copied into gesture-labelled directories using the script *a_move_labelled_data.m*, ensuring privacy and class consistency. A randomly generated ID is added to the files for anonymization and shuffling purposes. Source and destination folders, as well as gesture labels can be set using appropriate variables.
2. **Quality control** – The *b_training_data_analysis.m* script enables one to compute summary statistics (mean, median, variance, and range) for each gesture class. Samples deviating by $\pm 40\%$ (can be set using *thresholdRange* variable) from mean duration are flagged as outliers and plotted automatically for user's rapid evaluation. Two such indications for the gesture "Hold strong" are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Example of a QA routine output

3. **Truncation and alignment** – The script `c_training_data_truncation.m` provides an interactive tool for trimming initial latency caused by human reaction time, see Figure 4. If the truncation is necessary, the user needs to click on the displayed plot of sample signal to indicate where the gesture starts. A vertical dotted line is displayed as a result. After pressing the Enter key, the next sample is plotted. This allows to streamline processing of the recorded samples, given that the total number of recorded samples usually is at least in hundreds and manual adjusting in a spreadsheet editor or by other means would be too time-consuming.

Figure 4. Interactive tool for truncating the initial portion of data samples

4. **Windowing and augmentation** – Processed signals are segmented using a sliding window of 250 samples (2.5 s at 100 Hz) with a 50 sample step. Short sequences are looped to match window length rather than zero-padded, preserving physical signal properties. This step expanded the dataset from around 1300 to about 5600 training windows, significantly improving data density and model generalization capabilities. Figure 5 shows how a single signal with a total length of 700 can be divided into 10 distinct samples using such sliding window technique. The corresponding scripts can be found in `d_data_preparation.m`.

Figure 5. Sliding window method for training data segmentation

The windowing parameters are aligned with findings of other studies [30,31], who emphasize that the response should be fast enough. Moreover, this interval was confirmed by our initial tests, which have shown that 2.5 s was the least time that was necessary to distinguish between the gestures included in our training set. A separate script *e_train.m* was developed for conducting such manual training sessions to test particular parameters or architectures. It enables one to train a particular architecture and check its accuracy on validation data. This tool was particularly useful for the needs of the next subsection.

3.3. Model Development and Training

Architecture rationale

The model employs a One-Dimension Convolutional Neural Network (1D CNN) optimized for real-time embedded execution [59,60]. CNNs are chosen over recurrent models (e.g., LSTMs) due to their lower computational complexity and faster inference while maintaining comparable accuracy in temporal feature extraction. Several studies have shown a solid performance using more traditional approaches such as decision trees, and random forests [31]. However, these techniques require a selection of handcrafted features. As was pointed out in the introductory sections, our aim is to move from manual to fully automatic feature extraction in order to find correlations in multichannel data with cross-channel temporal correlations. In addition, CNNs support dilated convolutions, which helps to increase receptive field without increasing computational load if hardware resources are scarce. Thorough description of CNNs and their building blocks can be found in [49]. Comparison to traditional feature-based ML models (e.g., random forests) is described in greater detail in Section 3.4.

The script *e_train.m* described in the previous section came in particularly handy to test performance of different neural architectures, including LSTM and BiLSTM [61] on the gathered data. 1D CNN came out as the most promising candidate architecture in terms of computational complexity and model accuracy. This architecture was studied further, as described below.

Each network variant comprises an input layer, one to four convolutional layers (each linked to ReLU activation and batch normalization layers), followed by a fully connected layer and a softmax output layer. Convolutional dilation coefficients were varied to test long-term temporal sensitivity without increasing parameter count. Dilated convolution is an effective technique to increase receptive field of an CNN, particularly in resource-limited embedded systems [62], thus it was given a particular attention during this study.

The general idea during the experiments was to test as many materially diverse architectures as sensibly possible. Thus, architectures comprised variants with and without dilation, with various dilation coefficients, as well as a rather exotic *bottleneck* designs with a single filter at the first layer. The bottleneck design originated as a way to reduce parameter count and computational load by first reducing (squeezing) the number of filters, performing heavy computation in a narrower space, then expanding back [63]. It enables deeper networks with manageable resource use.

Hyperparameter exploration

Model development was conducted using *MATLAB Experiment Manager*, which systematically tested 13 CNN architectures under combinations of:

- 4 filter size sets, ranging from compact to large models;
- 3 epoch counts to test overfitting and effects of long training sessions;
- 3 training mini-batch sizes to test their influence on training process;
- 13 different network architectures were tested.

This generated 468 trained networks, each evaluated on held-out test data. The primary evaluation metric was classification accuracy, supplemented by computational efficiency indicators such as total parameters. The results are presented in the following sections.

Training setup

Training used 70% of the dataset for learning, 15% for validation, and 15% for testing final accuracy. The Adam optimizer with learning rate 0.001 was used throughout. No early stopping criteria were set at this point to run the tests for the total set number of epochs. The rationale was to ensure uniformity in model training for further comparison. Early stopping criteria are introduced at a later stage of the development in Section 4.4.

The current evaluation uses random splitting at the window level rather than strictly separating participants across training, validation, and testing sets. Consequently, the reported accuracies should be interpreted as upper bounds that may partially exploit participant-specific patterns.

The experiment was executed on a workstation equipped with two NVIDIA RTX 2070 GPUs, completing training in approximately 48 hours. The final models were ranked according to accuracy–complexity ratio to identify candidates suitable for microcontroller deployment.

3.4. Traditional Machine-learning Baselines

To complement the CNN-based approach, we evaluated several traditional ML classifiers on the same dataset. The goal was not only to benchmark accuracy, but also to assess model size and the need for handcrafted features in comparison with end-to-end 1D CNNs.

For the traditional ML experiments, the windowed dataset described in Section 3.2 was converted into a feature matrix. Each data sample corresponds to one 2.5 s window (250 samples at 100 Hz). In total, 88 features were computed per window across the 11 channels. For each channel, we extracted a compact set of time- and frequency-domain descriptors, including mean, standard deviation, minimum, maximum, root-mean-square (RMS), energy, and low-frequency bandpowers in the 0–1 Hz and 1–3 Hz bands. This yielded an 88-dimensional feature vector per gesture instance, summarizing both amplitude and slow temporal structure.

In addition to the feature-based representation described above, a trivial flattened raw windows representation was tested as well, where each 11×250 segment was reshaped into a 2750-dimensional vector. Furthermore, the feature-based representation was tested with and without principal component analysis (PCA) for dimensionality reduction.

Based on previously published reports [31], we have trained random forests, k-nearest neighbors (kNN), and support vector machines (SVMs). Validation used 5-fold cross-validation, ensuring that each sample was evaluated exactly once as part of a held-out fold. It should be noted that this protocol splits windows randomly and therefore does not enforce subject independence, and corresponds to the upper bound of the evaluation due to subject data leakage; subject-wise generalization is evaluated separately for the CNN using *leave-one-subject-out cross-validation* (LOSO-CV), where all the data from one particular subject are excluded from the training phase (Section 4.4).

For each classifier we recorded validation accuracy and the size of the trained model as reported by MATLAB. These characteristics were later used to compare traditional ML with the compact 1D CNNs in terms of accuracy, memory footprint, and deployment suitability on a MCU.

3.5. PC-Based Real-Time Simulation of the Obtained Models

Following training, selected CNN models were deployed in a real-time simulator implemented in MATLAB (*f_realtime_classifier.m*). GUI of this classifier is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. GUI of a real-time gesture classifier

The simulator establishes a real-time asynchronous data link with the interactive toy, which is continuously streaming sensor data. The simulator displays classification probabilities across gesture classes in real time. The GUI shows both the incoming signals and the current prediction with the highest ranking, as well as likelihood evaluations for all the classes. This enables qualitative evaluation of responsiveness and consistency. A single cumulative signal channel is plotted for the sake of speed and clarity. Prediction rate and plotted signal refresh rate can be set using appropriate variables.

3.6. Experiments

The experimental evaluation focused on identifying CNN architectures that provide the best trade-off between accuracy, speed, and resource use. All experiments were executed in *MATLAB Experiment Manager*, which automated hyperparameter exploration, training, and performance comparison. The developed scripts are available in the repository in folder "MATLAB Experiment Manager" [55].

3.6.1. Experimental Setup

The dataset described in Section 3 was used, consisting of 13-channel signals segmented into 250-sample sliding windows with 50-sample step. Data were divided into 70% training, 15% validation, and 15% testing subsets, ensuring balanced gesture representation.

The experiment is initialized using three MATLAB Live Scripts [55]:

- *PlushCNNExperimentInitialization.mlx* – data loading, normalization, and configuration setup.
- *PlushCNNExperiment.mlx* – architecture and hyperparameter management, including a parser of symbolic CNN architecture definitions.

- *metricAccuracy.mlx* – post-training evaluation of the model accuracy on held-out test data for the final ranking of the models.

Each CNN model was trained with the Adam optimizer (learning rate 0.001).

3.6.2. Hyperparameter Search

Thirteen CNN architectures were tested with different number of convolutional layers (1–4), dilation coefficients, and filter widths.

All the combinations of the following hyperparameters were tested during the experiment:

- **Number of filters by layer L1-L4:** [4 6 8 8], [8 12 16 16], [16 24 32 32], [32 48 64 64]; this range was deemed sufficient to test models from compact to large. Each number of these arrays sets filter size for the corresponding layer. If architecture has less than four convolutional layers, values for the deeper layers are ignored.
- **Epochs:** 100, 250, 1000; due to training data complexity and similarity of classes no satisfiable results were obtained with lesser epoch count during preliminary testing.
- **Mini-batch sizes:** 64, 256, 3936 (training set size during this experiment); testing various training strategies.
- **Architectural variations:** number of convolutional layers varied from 1 to 4, networks with and without dilation layers were tested with various filter counts; 13 different network architectures tested in total, as is described below in greater detail.

In order to facilitate experiment design and streamline experimentation and new topology definition, CNN architectures were defined symbolically using a particular syntax, which was parsed by the experimentation script: a number denotes filter size. If it is followed by a letter “d” and another number, it means that this layer has dilation with the indicated coefficient. Layers are separated by underscore “_”. For example, “83d1_84d2” corresponds to a network with two convolutional layers with 83 and 84 filters and dilation coefficients of 1 and 2, respectively. Here is the list of architectures that have been tested during the experiment: ["250", "126d2", "100_151", "83d1_84d2", "1d1_126d2", "70_90_91", "14d1_39d2_41d4", "28d1_32d2_41d4", "20d2_16d4_20d8", "19d1_24d3_19d9", "1d1_84d3_1d1", "1d1_27d3_20d9", "19d1_19d2_19d4_17d8"].

This produced 468 distinct experiment trials, each generating accuracy and loss data, which were automatically logged for comparison.

3.6.3. Evaluation Metrics

Two primary metrics guided model selection:

1. **Classification accuracy (ACC)** on held-out test data;
2. **Accuracy–Complexity Ratio (ACR)**, balancing predictive performance with parameter count, was used to test most promising models:

$$ACR = \frac{ACC}{\log_{10}(Parameters)}$$

Initial selection was made based on ACC alone to determine the most promising architectures. Afterwards efficiency was analyzed, using ACR.

Best performing models were then tested in a real-time classifier with a particular focus on compact models feasible for Edge deployment on MCUs.

Ethical Considerations – Institutional Review Board Statement

The study is conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Ethics Committee of the Research Committee of Riga Technical University (protocol code 04000-10.2.3-e/11 on March 25, 2025).

4. Results and Analysis

This section presents the quantitative and qualitative results of CNN-based affective gesture classification. First an overview of all the models is given, then a more thorough analysis follows with a particular focus on model complexity and its suitability for use in MCU environment.

4.1. Model Performance Overview

The experiment (see Section 3.6) produced 468 trained models across 13 CNN architectures and multiple hyperparameter sets. To give an overall evaluation of each architecture, Figure 7 shows the performance of each model is presented as the maximum value of accuracy on unseen test data as well as an average accuracy. Model size (in thousands of learnable parameters) for a network with number of filters at each convolution layer set as [L1:32; L2:48; L3:64; L4:64] is shown using a red dot, with the corresponding axis on the right-hand side.

Figure 7. Accuracy of the trained CNNs

As can be seen, models with dilated layers are clearly in the lead both regarding the maximum accuracy and the average accuracy, which is calculated across all the hyperparameter variations. Another observation is that bigger models do not necessarily perform better.

The number of filters influences greatly the size of the model. By testing various configurations indicated in Section 3.6.2, the range of the number of parameters in the tested models spans from 1.8k to 444k parameters. Thus, this range covers the models that are both suitable for workstations and for MCUs.

It should be noted that due to the computationally intensive nature of this experiment, results are based on random window-level splitting rather than subject-independent evaluation; they therefore represent upper-bound estimates, with subject-independent performance reported separately in Section 4.4.

4.2. Model Comparison by the Number of Parameters

Table 3 shows the number of parameters of each architecture depending on the number of filters in each layer. CNN architecture is given in the symbolic format that is explained in Section 3.6.2.

Table 3. Number of learnable parameters of the tested models depending on the number of filters

CNN architecture	Number of learnables for [32 48 64 64]	Number of learnables for [16 24 32 32]	Number of learnables for [8 12 16 16]	Number of learnables for [4 6 8 8]
14d1_39d2_41d4	192k	49.7k	13.2k	3.7k
28d1_32d2_41d4	186k	49.5k	13.8k	4.1k
19d1_24d3_19d9	103k	27.9k	8k	2.5k
19d1_19d2_19d4_17d8	165k	43.4k	11.8k	3.4k
20d2_16d4_20d8	95k	25.8k	7.5k	2.4k
83d1_84d2	160k	47.6k	15.7k	5.8k
100_151	169k	76.3k	23.6k	8.2k
1d1_27d3_20d9	105k	26.7k	6.9k	1.8k
126d2	46k	22.9k	11.4k	5.7k
1d1_126d2	195k	49.3k	12.5k	3.2k
1d1_84d3_1d1	134k	34k	8.7k	2.3k
70_90_91	444k	117.5k	32.6k	9.8k
250	90k	44.8k	22.4k	11.2k

Figure 8 shows the performance of models separately for each with the number of filters tested during the experiment.

(a) [32 48 64 64]

(b) [16 24 32 32]

(c) [8 12 16 16]

(d) [4 6 8 8]

Figure 8. Performance of models, depending on the number of filters in each layer:

(a) [32 48 64 64]; (b) [16 24 32 32]; (c) [8 12 16 16]; (d) [4 6 8 8]

While only the bigger models with number of filters [32 48 64 64] were close to accuracy of 80% - architecture 14d1_39d2_41d4 demonstrated accuracy of 79.03%, their size makes them unfit for embedded systems with scarce computational power and limited memory capacity.

However, as can be seen in Figure 8(b-d), smaller models have demonstrated solid performance with several models reaching accuracy higher than 70%. Remarkably, top three performers in all the size classes, excluding the smallest one, were these three models: 14d1_39d2_41d4, 19d1_24d3_19d9, and 28d1_32d2_41d4.

The only model in the smallest size class was the four-layer model 19d1_19d2_19d4_17d8, which had the maximum accuracy of 72.75%.

Table 4 summarizes the top three performance in all the size classes.

Table 4. Top three performance in all the model size classes with accuracy > 70%

Symbolic 1D-CNN architecture (see Sect. 4.2)	Number of filters per layer L1 L2 L3 [L4]	Number of parameters	Maximum accuracy on test data	Average accuracy across hyperparameters	ACR (see Sect. 4.3)
14d1_39d2_41d4	32 48 64	192k	79.0%	66.7%	15.0%
19d1_24d3_19d9	32 48 64	103k	77.1%	69.4%	15.4%
28d1_32d2_41d4	32 48 64	186k	77.1%	68.2%	14.6%
14d1_39d2_41d4	8 12 16	13.2k	75.0%	65.7%	18.2%
19d1_24d3_19d9	16 24 32	27.9k	74.1%	65.5%	16.7%
28d1_32d2_41d4	8 12 16	13.8k	73.6%	68.2%	17.8%
19d1_19d2_19d4_17d8	4 6 8 8	3.4k	72.7%	59.1%	20.6%
14d1_39d2_41d4	16 24 32	49.7k	72.4%	67.2%	15.4%
28d1_32d2_41d4	16 24 32	49.5k	72.3%	67.4%	15.4%
19d1_24d3_19d9	8 12 16	8k	71.7%	63.5%	18.4%
28d1_32d2_41d4	4 6 8	4.1k	69.1%	57.0%	19.1%
70_90_91	4 6 8	9.8k	68.7%	56.7%	17.2%

Graphical representation of the top performers across all the architectures is shown in Figure 9

Figure 9. Accuracy and size of top performers

Based on these data, *14d1_39d2_41d4* architecture was selected for further analysis, as it demonstrates a solid performance with accuracy on unseen test data of 75% with only a fraction of learnable parameters, which is 13.2k. This level of accuracy was reached after 250 epochs, learning algorithm used *MiniBatchSize=64*. Due to its compactness, it has a high *ACR* value of 18.2%.

Also notable is the model *19d1_19d2_19d4_17d8*, which at only 3.4k parameters has even higher *ACR* of 20.6%, but has lower, although still solid performance with 72.7% accuracy.

By using dilation factors 1-3-9 in a three-layer model *19d1_24d3_19d9* allowed reducing the number of parameters to 8k, which ensured a high *ACR* value of 18.4%. However, this model has lower accuracy (71.7%) than its 1-2-4 three-layer counterpart mentioned above. Another small model has *ACR* of 19.1%, but is not considered during further analysis, since its accuracy is under 70%.

The main takeaway from this preliminary analysis is that increasing the number of parameters even by orders of magnitude, does not increase the performance of the model substantially. This means that these models show the highest possible performance, given the noise, ambiguities and conflicts in the data. Source of these ambiguities is the fact that the gestures were subject to person's interpretation. And given that some of them are very similar, the performance of the different gestures by different individuals occasionally overlaps. This is more clearly demonstrated in the next Section 4.3.

It is important to mention that the values obtained during this experiment, due to its computationally intensive nature, were not subject to cross-validation. However, due to the repetitive nature of the experiment, some general conclusions can be drawn about the tested models. Three-layer models with dilated layers have shown the strongest performance across the tested hyperparameters. As can be seen in Table 4, the three architectures *14d1_39d2_41d4*, *19d1_24d3_19d9*, and *28d1_32d2_41d4* dominate the top performers and appear multiple times in the list.

4.3. Confusion Matrix Analysis

Confusion matrix obtained using the *14d1_39d2_41d4* model is shown in Figure 10. As can be seen, apart from occasional noise, there are a few of classification "clusters", where the classes are confused more often. One such example is gesture Head stroke 1/2, which differ only by the location of the interactive toy – either in a person's hands or on a table. Same with the gesture Neck scratch 1/2. On the other hand,

Figure 11. Confusion matrix for 19d1_19d2_19d4_17d8

Confusion matrix for the model 19d1_19d2_19d4_17d8 share similar characteristics and is shown in Figure 11.

Gesture-level performance showed strong separability between most gestures that have distinct spatial and temporal profiles. Confusions were observed either in gestures that have similar signal profiles, such as *Tail scratch* and *Tail tap*, or in the same gesture that was performed under different conditions, namely while the toy was held in hands or sit on a table (e.g. *Head stroke 1/2*).

4.4. Subject-Independent Evaluation with Leave-One-Subject-Out Cross-Validation

To quantify generalization to unseen users and address subject data leakage concerns, we performed *leave-one-subject-out cross-validation* (LOSO-CV) on the selected CNN architecture 14d1_39d2_41d4 with 8, 12, and 16 filters in the three convolutional layers (Section 4.2), since it had the highest accuracy among the compact models. The LOSO protocol used the same windowed dataset as the main experiments that was obtained from 25 subjects. In each fold, all windows from one subject were held out for testing, while the remaining 24 subjects were split into training and validation sets.

It is important to note that, in contrast to the initial architecture-search experiments described in Section 3.6, where uniformity was important, the LOSO-CV training protocol employed an improved and more robust optimization schedule. Specifically, training used an adaptive learning-rate scheme with an initial rate of 0.003, piecewise decay by a factor of 0.5 every 30 epochs; in addition early stopping was introduced based on validation stagnation, with *validation patience* equal to 10. The maximum number of epochs was set to 150 and was never reached. Most models required 50-80 epochs for training. This increased training efficiency and reduced overfitting risk.

For every fold we trained the CNN from scratch and evaluated performance on the held-out subject. We report fold-wise accuracy, as well as macro-averaged recall and F1 score computed across all 18 classes. This yields a stringent estimate of inter-subject generalization, where no data from the test subject is seen during training or validation.

Across 25 folds, the model achieved:

- Mean LOSO accuracy: 0.850 ± 0.072
- Mean LOSO macro recall: 0.717 ± 0.111
- Mean LOSO macro F1: 0.687 ± 0.114

Using the aggregated confusion matrix over all folds, we obtained:

- Overall micro accuracy: 0.847
- Overall macro recall: 0.691
- Overall macro F1: 0.701

Per-class metrics showed strong performance for most positive and neutral gestures, including *At rest* (F1 = 0.984), *Head stroke 1* (F1 = 0.892), *Neck scratch 1* (F1 = 0.815), and *Ear scratch 1* (F1 = 0.791). Lower scores were observed for several tail-related gestures such as *Tail hit 2* (F1 = 0.465), *Tail scratch 2* (F1 = 0.498), and *Tail tap 2* (F1 = 0.606), which either are short and energetic or low-amplitude gestures with partially overlapping signal profiles. These confusions are consistent with qualitative observations from real-time testing (Section 4.6). It confirms the need to introduce a threshold-based filter to catch trivial, short, and energetic gestures, as well as to combine similar gestures to increase overall accuracy, where both gestures fall into the same class (positive/negative/neutral). The LOSO-CV results demonstrate that the selected 1D CNN maintains robust performance under a strict subject-independent evaluation protocol.

4.5. Comparison with Traditional Machine-Learning Baselines

Traditional ML classifiers were evaluated both on flattened window data and on the feature-based dataset described in Section 3.4. All results in this subsection are based on 5-fold cross-validation with random splits over windows; therefore, they are not strictly subject-independent and are likely to slightly overestimate generalization compared to LOSO-CV.

Using flattened raw windows (2750 features), several models reached high validation accuracy but at the cost of substantial model size. For instance, a cubic SVM and random forest achieved 90.4% and 89.7% accuracy, respectively, but at the model size of 259 MB and 28 MB of memory. Subspace kNN reached 89.3% accuracy with a reported model footprint (MATLAB) of approximately 2 GB. Such models are unsuitable for deployment on the ESP32 microcontroller, which offers only a few megabytes of RAM and flash.

When switching to the feature-based representation (88 features per sample) and keeping 5-fold CV, performance improved further while revealing clearer trade-offs between accuracy and model size. Without PCA, random forest achieved 95.9% accuracy with 10 MB model size.

Enabling PCA on the same feature set drastically reduced validation accuracy across all models (in particular, to 66.3% for random forest). This underscores the difficulty of performing manual dimensionality reduction for these signals and highlights the need for models that can learn task-specific low-dimensional representations directly from the data.

Taken together, these results show that feature-based classical methods can achieve high accuracy, sometimes comparable to or even slightly exceeding the CNN's LOSO performance. However it should be emphasized that these tests have been performed using random 5-fold CV that mixes data from the same subjects between training and validation. They also require handcrafted feature engineering and, in the case of ensemble methods and SVMs, often exceed the memory constraints of the embedded platform. In contrast, the selected 1D CNN operates directly on raw windowed sensor data, requires no handcrafted

features, fits comfortably within the memory budget of the chosen ESP32 MCU, and has been validated under a much stricter subject-independent protocol.

4.6. PC-Based Real-Time Classifier Validation

The *14d1_39d2_41d4* model selected in Section 4.2 has been tested using the PC-based real-time simulator described in Section 3.5, with the physical toy connected via Bluetooth as a live sensor data source.

To evaluate how the trained 1D-CNN behaves under realistic interaction conditions, we conducted a PC-based real-time simulation study with five new participants (two adult males, one adult female, one teenage male, one teenage female). None of these subjects were included in the training sets. Each participant repeated the full gesture protocol used during data collection – performing all 17 gestures (gesture "At rest" was not performed, since it does not intend human interaction), each three times in a controlled sequence. During each gesture, we recorded (i) the activation level of the 1D-CNN classifier in range [0;1], (ii) the response of the heuristic threshold-based algorithm, and (iii) the reaction time of each method. Reaction times were measured manually at the moment when the CNN output first produced a stable class activation; this introduces a measurement uncertainty of approximately ± 0.3 s, but the variance was sufficiently small to preserve relative trends across gesture types.

This qualitative validation was intentionally small-scale, involving five participants, and serves as a proof-of-concept rather than a statistically powered evaluation.

Performance on broad, well-defined gestures

Both algorithms performed reliably on gestures characterized by large, distinct sensor signatures such as *Back stroke* and *Head stroke*. The heuristic algorithm activated in approximately 90% of trials, with an average reaction time of ~ 3 s, while the CNN consistently produced class-specific activation within roughly 2.0–2.2 s. These outcomes align with the high per-class F1 scores reported in LOSO-CV for these gesture families.

Performance on subtle, fine-grained gestures

For gestures involving small or fingertip-driven motions – *Ear scratch*, *Neck scratch*, and *Tail scratch* – the CNN demonstrated a clear advantage. It activated in all trials, producing coherent class-likelihood patterns across participants. Misclassification occurred only within the same gesture family: in about 13% of *Tail scratch* repetitions, the model signaled *Tail tap*, reflecting the similarity of these low-amplitude contact patterns. By contrast, the heuristic algorithm responded in only $\sim 6\%$ of such trials, confirming that finely structured tactile signatures require learned temporal features rather than simple rule-based activations. CNN activation levels were typically in the 0.75–0.88 range for these gestures, occasionally reaching 0.98 with stabilization times of 2.3–2.4 s, matching expectations from the offline per-class metrics.

Performance on energetic negative gestures

For high-energy aversive gestures – *Tail hit* and *Tail pull* – the behaviour reversed. The heuristic algorithm reacted almost instantaneously (0.1–0.2 s) in all trials due to the abrupt, high-amplitude change in sensor signal values. The CNN also detected these gestures reliably but with significantly longer stabilization times (2.0–2.5 s) and more variable activation dynamics. These results confirm prior observations that sudden extreme deviations in sensor values are most efficiently detected by simple threshold logic rather than a sequential classifier.

Performance on neutral gestures

Neutral gestures such as *Hold in hands* are not processed by the heuristic algorithm and therefore do not elicit any response. The CNN, however, consistently produced stable activations for these gestures, with average reaction times of about 2.4 s and mean likelihood values around 0.83, consistent across all participants.

Implications for system design

The real-time results show that the CNN reproduces its behavior predictably across new users, while also revealing gesture-specific latency profiles. Together with LOSO-CV outcomes, these findings support the adoption of a hybrid classifier architecture in which a fast threshold-based captures trivial high-energy events (e.g., *Tail hit*, *Tail pull*), while the 1D-CNN handles the full taxonomy of subtle and neutral gestures.

Overall, the real-time validation demonstrates that the 1D-CNN is operationally stable, produces consistent gesture-specific activation across users, and offers a substantial advantage over heuristic methods for subtle and neutral gesture categories, while threshold methods remain preferable for extreme high-amplitude events.

4.7. Suitability for Embedded Design

Two main characteristics must be analyzed when deploying a model on an embedded system: memory requirements and computational load.

As can be seen in Table 4, the selected models are quite compact and occupy only around 14-53KB of memory even before quantization.

On the other hand, quantization should be strongly considered in case an MCU does not have a floating-point accelerator. Since our design uses *ESP32-WROVER-E* that does not have FP accelerator, the model will be quantized, because it should have real-time performance capability.

In order to estimate real-time performance, it is necessary to calculate model's MACs that are required for a single inference. To illustrate this, consider the model *14d1_39d2_41d4* with the number of filters respectively 8, 12, and 16. The calculated MAC for such a model is around 3.2 MMAC.

From the published benchmark data [64], the following performance of ESP32 MCUs has been calculated: 58MMAC/s for floating-point operations; 137MMAC/s for Int16 operations. This implies *55ms* inference time for floating-point model and *23ms* for quantized model. However, these are benchmark evaluations. Actual experiments with quantized neural models show a 4-5x increase in processing speed attributed to quantization [65]. Such performance allows it to be used to make inferences with *50ms* steps, exactly as the models were tested in the real-time simulator on a workstation.

Although the computational and memory budget of the embedded platform has been analyzed in detail, it is important to note that the reported inference times are estimates based on ESP32 performance benchmarks, rather than direct measurements. This is intentional and consistent with the scope of the present work, which focuses on the design and validation of the gesture-recognition model itself – including architecture development, cross-validation, and generalization analysis. The physical integration of the trained model into the MCU on the actual hardware platform along with field tests will be addressed in a separate study.

5. Discussion

The presented results confirm that compact 1D CNN architectures can provide accurate, low-latency affective gesture recognition on microcontroller-class hardware. The top models achieved accuracy close to 80%, with compact models being in the 72-75% range, and 23ms estimated inference time.

5.1. Model efficiency, generalization, and comparison with classical methods

The proposed CNN outperformed the previous heuristic system during the classification of subtle, gentle touches. Both systems have shown similar results when classifying straightforward, well-defined gestures. As expected, the trivial threshold-based system outperformed other systems by detecting abrupt, sudden gestures, which involve energetic movements. The CNN model has 2.5 s receptive field, which was empirically determined to be sufficient to classify gestures in the collected dataset.

Theoretical estimates show that quantized inference on the ESP32-WROVER-E can be made at 20Hz, suggesting that real-time affective tactile classification entirely on-device, without the need to transfer signal data or use cloud or external computation, is achievable within the hardware constraints of the chosen platform. Modest memory requirements make these models suitable for edge affective computing, where emotional interpretation is performed locally to ensure privacy, low latency, and reliability.

Analysis of confusion matrices indicates that gesture confusions were mostly related to gestures with similar signal patterns, or to the same gestures that were performed while the toy was held in hands or stayed on a table.

In addition to the initial train-validation-test split used for architecture search, the chosen CNN architecture was evaluated using LOSO-CV. Across 25 folds and 18 gesture classes, the model achieved a mean accuracy of 0.850 ± 0.072 and a mean macro-F1 score of 0.687 ± 0.114 . These results demonstrate that the model generalizes well to unseen users, even under strict subject-independent conditions, and address the risk of subject data leakage that is inherent in random train-test splits for windowed time-series data.

The per-class analysis shows that most positive and neutral gestures, such as head and neck strokes or ear scratches, are recognized reliably, while performance is weaker for some either short or low-amplitude subtle gestures that are intrinsically ambiguous. This pattern is consistent with the confusions observed in the real-time qualitative evaluation, where subtle tail taps and scratches were also harder to distinguish consistently than broad strokes.

Traditional ML baselines trained on handcrafted features achieved high 5-fold cross-validation accuracy, with random forest model achieving 95.9% accuracy but requiring around 10 MB of memory. However, these results must be interpreted with caution. First, the 5-fold CV splits mix windows from the same subjects between training and validation, which can inflate performance compared to subject-wise LOSO-CV. Second, all feature-based methods depend on a manually designed feature set. In contrast, the 1D CNN operates directly on multichannel raw windows and learns internal representations tailored to the classification task.

Finally, the poor performance of PCA-based variants of the classical models, which all dropped to around 65% accuracy despite dimensionality reduction, indicates that naive variance-based compression discards task-relevant structure. This supports the choice of convolutional architectures with dilated receptive fields, which can exploit subtle temporal and cross-channel correlations in the raw signals without relying on brittle manual dimensionality reduction.

5.2. Proposed Embedded Optimization Strategy

Although the obtained models are already rather compact and do not require quantization for memory efficiency purposes, it is advisable to quantize the model in the forthcoming hardware implementation to achieve higher computational performance, because the chosen MCU does not have a FP accelerator.

Furthermore, the results of this study suggest adopting a two-stage processing strategy for the future hardware implementation, which would combine a trivial and computationally light threshold-rule-based heuristic filtering for energetic gestures, coupled to CNN inference at the second stage for classification of more complex and subtle gestures. This would ensure both instantaneous reaction to easy-to-catch gestures and accurate classification of more complex and gentle gestures.

Such an approach is expected to support real-time operation within ESP32 MCU resource constraints while leaving capacity for concurrent control and signaling routines, and will be validated through direct hardware implementation and measurement in a forthcoming study.

6. Conclusions and Future Work

This study demonstrated a complete end-to-end pipeline for the development of an embedded deep learning system for real-time affective touch recognition using a soft interactive toy. It covers training data

acquisition, data analysis, cleaning, preparation, as well as routines both for manual network definition and testing, and for large-scale automated experiments that sweep through hundreds of hyperparameter combinations. A PC-based real-time simulation environment was developed, enabling qualitative validation of the trained models using live sensor data streamed from the physical toy via Bluetooth. The complete open-source MATLAB pipeline, constituting a reusable framework for developing and testing ML models for affective touch recognition in smart interactive companions, is publicly available at a repository [55].

To train and evaluate the model, a multichannel dataset of affective gestures was collected, comprising 1326 labelled recordings from 25 participants spanning diverse demographics including children, teenagers, and adults. The dataset is publicly available and published in accordance with FAIR principles [54], constituting an independent contribution of this work that can support future research in affective touch recognition.

Extensive study of 1D CNN network architectures has been performed by running 468 trials in order to test 13 CNN architectures. Most promising architecture types were determined and best performing architectures were studied in greater detail.

The obtained models were validated in a PC-based real-time simulator using live sensor data from the physical toy. Physical integration of the trained model into the MCU-based embedded system, along with fine-tuning and field testing in therapeutic sessions with children with ASD, is designated as the subject of a forthcoming study.

The additional experiments with traditional ML baselines and subject-independent evaluation further clarify the role of 1D CNNs in the proposed system. Feature-based decision trees, ensembles, and shallow neural networks can achieve high accuracy under random 5-fold cross-validation, but they either require large model footprints that exceed the capabilities of the embedded platform or depend on handcrafted features that are costly to maintain as the system evolves. The compact 1D CNN evaluated with leave-one-subject-out cross-validation offers a stronger guarantee of generalization to unseen users while remaining computationally lightweight and feature-agnostic. Future work will extend this evaluation to longer-term real-time deployments and clinical or educational field trials, where the embedded classifier will be tested in therapy sessions with children with ASD alongside the behavioral and qualitative outcomes reported in our companion study.

The work advances the field of affective robotics by demonstrating that tactile emotion recognition can be implemented efficiently at the edge, within the physical substrate of a soft interactive system. The methodological framework – comprising automated data capture, sliding-window augmentation, CNN optimization, and real-time validation – provides a reusable template for future low-cost affective devices.

The integration of deep learning with soft tactile sensing demonstrates a viable pathway toward emotionally intelligent, resource-efficient interactive companions. By achieving reliable on-device affective classification, the proposed system brings affective therapeutic technology closer to patients – establishing a foundation for emotionally aware devices that respond naturally, safely, and autonomously through touch.

Glossary

1D CNN	— One-Dimensional Convolutional Neural Network
ACC	— Classification Accuracy
ACR	— Accuracy–Complexity Ratio
ASD	— Autism Spectrum Disorder
BiLSTM	— Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory
CNN	— Convolutional Neural Network
CSV	— Comma-Separated Values
CV	— Cross-Validation
ECG	— Electrocardiogram
FAIR	— Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FP	— Floating Point
GUI	— Graphical User Interface

kNN	— k-Nearest Neighbors
LED	— Light-Emitting Diode
LOSO-CV	— Leave-One-Subject-Out Cross-Validation
LSTM	— Long Short-Term Memory
MCU	— Microcontroller Unit
ML	— Machine Learning
MMAC	— Million Multiply-Accumulate Operations
PCA	— Principal Component Analysis
ReLU	— Rectified Linear Unit
RMS	— Root Mean Square
SAR	— Socially Assistive Robot
SVM	— Support Vector Machine

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Aleksandrs Vališevskis: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Writing-Original draft, Visualization, Investigation. **Aleksandrs Okss:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing-Review & Editing. **Inese Tiģere:** Methodology, Writing-Review & Editing. **Aleksejs Kataševs:** Conceptualization, Methodology. **Dina Bethere:** Methodology, Project administration, **Anete Hofmane:** Methodology, Validation. **Airisa Šteinberga:** Methodology, Validation. **Undīne Gavriļenko:** Methodology, Validation. **Santa Meļķe:** Validation. **Lucie Matoušková:** Validation.

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Data Availability Statement

The original dataset presented in this study is openly available in Zenodo at [54]. The complete software pipeline developed for this study is openly available in Zenodo at [55]. Both are published in accordance with FAIR principles.

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